

Localized Versus Collective Behaviour of *d*-Electrons in Transition Metal Oxide Systems of Perovskite Structure*

C. N. R. RAO**

Jawaharlal Nehru Fellow, Indian Institute of Technology, Kanpur 208016

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The behaviour of *d*-electrons in perovskites of the type LnZO_3 (Z =trivalent transition metal ion and Ln =rare earth or yttrium) depends on the spin configuration of the transition metal ion. LaTiO_3 and LaNiO_3 with low-spin transition metal ions ($S=\frac{1}{2}$) are metallic while LnCrO_3 , LnMnO_3 and LnFeO_3 with high-spin ions are poor semiconductors exhibiting localized behaviour of *d*-electrons. In rare earth cobaltites, the cobalt ions are present mainly in the diamagnetic low-spin Co^{III} state at low temperatures. The Co^{III} ions transform to high-spin Co^{3+} ions with increase in temperature. At higher temperatures, there is electron-transfer from Co^{3+} to Co^{III} ions producing intermediate states. We see spin-state transitions in these cobaltites in the range 250-870 K. At high temperatures, the cobaltites show evidence for localized-itinerant electron transitions. In $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ there is onset of ferromagnetism at $x>0.125$, at which point there is a structural discontinuity and electrons become itinerant. The composition with $x=0.5$ is metallic and $T_c=230$ K. The ferromagnetic component in $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ increases with x in the range 0.125-0.50. Catalytic properties of rare earth cobaltites appear to be related to the spin state equilibria.

TRANSITION metal oxides with the perovskite structure have been studied extensively in recent years¹⁻⁶ because of their interesting electronic and magnetic properties. These studies have led to the conclusion that if the cationic spin $S \leq \frac{1}{2}$, the oxides would exhibit metallic conductivity and Pauli paramagnetism. The *d*-electrons in such systems exhibiting collective behaviour are well described by band theory. On the other hand, if $S \geq 2$, the oxides have an atomic moment which can be described by crystal field theory and in such cases the *d*-electrons behave as localized electrons. Jahn-Teller distortion is found in the case where there are four *d*-electrons ($S=2$). The factors which determine the spin state (low or high) of the transition metal ion in a given substance are essentially the crystal field splitting Δ_{cr} and the exchange energy Δ_{ex} . Ions exist in the low-spin or high-spin state depending on whether Δ_{cr} is greater or less than Δ_{ex} . When $\Delta_{\text{cr}} > \Delta_{\text{ex}}$, the low-spin state is the stable state as in WO_3 and CaVO_3 . When $\Delta_{\text{cr}} < \Delta_{\text{ex}}$, the transition metal ions exist in the high-spin state as in LaCrO_3 , LaMnO_3 , etc. When $\Delta_{\text{cr}} \approx \Delta_{\text{ex}}$, however, both the spin states can coexist.

In the covalent crystal field approach, the parameter which determines the localized or collective behaviour of the *d*-electrons is the magnitude of overlap integrals, Δ_{cao} . In terms of the overlap integrals, the situation $\Delta_{\text{cr}} \approx \Delta_{\text{ex}}$ can be found when the integrals Δ_{cao} and Δ_{cae} are of the right order. If the overlap integrals are large enough, it is appropriate to construct collective electron orbitals out of the orbitals of e_g and t_{2g} symmetry. These two approaches as shown by Liehr⁷, are different descriptions of the same phenomenon and suggest the existence of low-spin or collective electrons when Δ_{cr} is large, and that of high-spin or localized electrons when Δ_{cr} is small. Thus, the crystal field theory and band theory provide the two limiting descriptions of *d*-electrons.

A variety of transition metal oxide systems, particularly those possessing the perovskite structure have been found to exhibit either localized or collective electron behaviour of the *d*-electrons. We

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** Commonwealth Visiting Professor, Oxford University St. Catherines College, Oxford, England.

shall now examine in detail, various perovskites of the general formula LnZO_3 (Ln=rare earth ion, Z=transition metal ion) with different transition metal ions: LnTiO_3 , LnCrO_3 , LnMnO_3 , LnFeO_3 , LaCoO_3 and LaNiO_3 . In these, LaTiO_3 and LaNiO_3 have low-spin transition metal ions ($S=\frac{1}{2}$), while LaCrO_3 , LaMnO_3 and LaFeO_3 have high-spin ions. However, in LaCoO_3 , where $\Delta_{\text{cf}} \approx \Delta_{\text{ex}}$ (or $\Delta_{\text{vac}}^{\sigma}$ and $\Delta_{\text{vac}}^{\pi}$ are of the right order), both the low- and the high-spin states can coexist, thereby imparting interesting electrical and magnetic properties. In such a system, we would expect to observe a transition from localized to collective electron behaviour. LaCoO_3 which exhibits some unique electrical and magnetic properties^{8, 9-10}, is one of the few oxide materials where such a localized electron \rightleftharpoons collective electron transition has indeed been suggested to occur^{8, 9}.

Racah and Goodenough⁸ have shown that LaCoO_3 undergoes a first order transition around 1210 K due to a change from localized behaviour of d -electrons to collective behaviour. Beyond this transition, where the bonding e_g electrons form a σ^* band, LaCoO_3 becomes metallic. Goodenough⁸ has interpreted the electron transport and other properties of LaCoO_3 in terms of the temperature-variation of spin- and valence-state equilibria of cobalt ions and has suggested that the $e_g \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transition implies that the crystal field and band limits of d -electrons are distinct thermodynamic states. Goodenough's mechanism for electrical conduction in LaCoO_3 presumes the formation of high-spin divalent cobalt and low-spin tetravalent cobalt ion pairs. Many aspects of Goodenough's mechanism do not have direct experimental evidence. I shall present in this paper, results of a detailed and systematic investigation of well-characterised samples of LaCoO_3 by employing a variety of techniques including differential thermal analysis, x-ray diffraction, magnetic susceptibility and electron transport properties as well as Mossbauer spectroscopy. Among these different techniques, Mossbauer spectroscopy provides a direct method to identify the various valence and spin states of cobalt.

As we go along the rare earth series from lanthanum to lutecium, the size of the rare earth ion decreases whereas the acidity increases. We shall examine the effect of the central rare earth ion on the transport properties of the various LnZO_3

systems, as well as on the spin state equilibria in rare earth cobaltites. It is of particular interest to see if the $e_g \rightarrow \sigma^*$ electronic transition found in LaCoO_3 is also seen in other cobaltites.

Jonker and Van Santen¹¹ first showed that $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ (LaCoO_3 is the end member of this system with $x=0$) becomes ferromagnetic for $x>0.15$ and associated the ferromagnetism with the concentration of tetravalent cobalt which increases with Sr^{2+} concentration. Further, when $x=0.5$, the oxide becomes metallic with bronze lustre. The paramagnetic susceptibility of this system could be explained by the Curie-Weiss and with θ changing from a negative to a positive value around $x=0.15$. However, the magnitude of magnetization and paramagnetic Curie temperatures could not be reconciled with the then existing theory. Goodenough¹², assuming the 3d electrons to be localized, interpreted the ferromagnetism by modifying the superexchange model of Anderson¹³. According to Goodenough, a 180° superexchange interaction $\text{Co}^{3+}(t_{2g}^5 e_g^2) - \text{O}^{2-} - \text{CO}^{\text{IV}}(t_{2g}^5 e_g^0)$ would be ferromagnetic. However, Goodenough^{3, 4} has later pointed out that covalent mixing between the transition metal d -orbitals and oxygen 2p orbitals may enhance the superexchange interaction sufficiently to break down the conditions for localized d -electrons. It is now indeed known that delocalization of d -electrons is very much prevalent in transition metal oxides, particularly in those with perovskite structure, than suspected earlier^{3, 4, 6}. Studies on LaCoO_3 referred to earlier clearly bring out the localized versus collective behaviour of the d electrons in such oxides. Studies on $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ by Racah and Goodenough¹⁴ showed the $e_g \rightarrow \sigma^*$ transition of LaCoO_3 persists to relatively high values of x , the enthalpy change decreasing with x as expected for a two phase mixture, although they found no crystallographic evidence for two phases (at $x=0.5$, the solid becomes metallic). These observations led Racah and Goodenough¹⁴ to the conjecture that whereas all the electrons in the σ^- bonding orbitals are delocalized at the highest temperature, at low temperatures, some of the electrons get trapped as localized e_g electrons at Co^{3+} ions in the La^{3+} -rich regions. They also associated the ferromagnetism in $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ with the Sr^{2+} -rich regions and paramagnetism with the La^{3+} -rich regions. I shall presently discuss recent studies in this laboratory

which clearly elucidate the various conceptual problems raised by the $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ system which exhibits both ferromagnetism and itinerant electron behaviour at large x .

In addition to discussing the various oxide systems mentioned earlier, I shall briefly present some aspects related to the catalytic activity of rare earth cobaltites. The cobaltites are recently reported to be good catalysts for the oxidation of carbon monoxide.

Rare Earth Chromites, Manganites and Ferrites :

All these perovskites except the heavy rare earth manganites are orthorhombic. LnCrO_3 and LnFeO_3 are anti-ferromagnetic with superimposed weak ferromagnetism. The Neel temperatures, T_N , of LnCrO_3 are low (below room temperature whereas LnFeO_3 show relatively high values (~ 640 K). The crystallographic and magnetic properties of these perovskites have been well investigated. We have carried out a systematic examination of the electronic spectra (in the range $30,000\text{--}11,000\text{ cm}^{-1}$), the infrared spectra (range $4,000\text{--}30\text{ cm}^{-1}$), electrical conductivity, σ and Seebeck coefficient, α (as a function of temperature and oxygen partial pressure) and dielectric (hysteresis and pyroelectric current) properties of these three series of perovskites in the form of polycrystalline materials (and single crystals in some cases) not only as an aid to supplement the available literature data but also to gain insight into the mechanism of conduction in these solid state materials^{15,16}.

The electronic and infra-red spectra of the rare earth perovskites¹⁵ indicate that they are characteristic of the parent transition metal oxides slightly modified by the presence of the rare earth ion in the lattice. The electronic spectra are characteristic of the transition metal ions and are readily explained by ligand field theory.¹⁵ Characteristic variations in the observed spectra can be interpreted in terms of the variation of metal-oxygen covalency effects of Z-O and Ln-O bonds. The covalency of the Z-O bond decreases with increase in the atomic number from Cr to Fe within the rare earth series and Ln-O covalency seems to vary significantly from La to Lu. There is some indication from the spectra that there is distortion in the ZO_6 polyhedra in the heavier rare earth chromites and manganites.

The LnZO_3 perovskites ($Z = \text{Cr, Mn or Fe}$) are

p-type semiconductors with conductivity in the range exhibited by the parent transition metal oxides ($10^{-4}\text{--}10^{-1}\text{ ohm}^{-1}\text{ cm}^{-1}$), but considerably higher than the parent rare earth sesquioxides (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Plot of logarithm of electrical conductivity (in micromhs cm^{-1}) of HoZO_3 , against reciprocal of absolute temperature. Activation energies are indicated.

Among the three series, the chromites have the highest conductivity at a given temperature. Within the rare earth series, however, σ decreases with increase in the atomic number of the Ln as in the case of Ln-sesquioxides and the energy of activation for conduction, E_a , increases¹⁶. Breaks in $\log \sigma\text{--}1/T$ plots are noted at known crystallographic and dielectric transition temperatures. The measured Seebeck coefficients ($\sim 0.3\text{ mV}/^\circ\text{C}$ and independent of temperature), the low E_a values ($0.05\text{--}0.25\text{ eV}$), the estimated mobilities ($10^{-5}\text{--}10^{-8}\text{ cm}^2/\text{V}\cdot\text{sec}$) and electronic spectra (bands characteristic of Z^{3+} ion) all point to the fact that the LnZO_3 compounds are narrow band materials (small polaron) exhibiting localized *d*-electron behaviour. No intrinsic conduction is encountered in these oxides up to the maximum temperature investigated (1200 K). For all practical purposes, the *d*-electrons of the transition element control the optical and electrical properties of these perovskites and Ln plays only a minor role. The conclusions are in accord with the Goodenough scheme shown in the one-electron energy diagram in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Schematic one electron energy diagram for LaCrO_3 (after Goodenough). Numbers brackets represent states per molecule for band scheme. Numbers in parentheses represent weighting factor for the oxygen spatial orbitals. Atomic levels are shown split by the crystalline fields. Δ_{ex} represents the exchange splitting; Δ_{ex} is always greater than $10 Dq$ for high spin Mn^{2+} and Fe^{2+} and possibly for Cr^{2+} . In LaMnO_3 and LaFeO_3 , the narrow band becomes the localized e_g levels as shown in figure. The diagram essentially remains the same for the other rare earth chromites, manganites and ferrites.

The heavy rare earth manganites which are hexagonal and ferroelectric show breaks in $\log \sigma - 1/T$ plots at the known ferroelectric Curie points. In the heavy rare earth chromites we note similar breaks at high temperatures which could not be identified as involving crystallographic or magnetic transitions. We suspect that these may represent ferroelectric \rightarrow paraelectric transitions. Dielectric hysteresis loop and pyroelectric current measurements also confirm that these materials are associated with ferroelectricity just as the heavy rare earth manganites.

LaTiO₃ and LaNiO₃ : LaTiO_3 and LaNiO_3 with the transition metal ions in the low-spin ($S=1/2$) state are expected to exhibit collective behaviour of d -electrons. They are both indeed metallic (Fig. 3) and Pauli paramagnetic. Studies on NdTiO_3 and other titanites also show that the itinerant regime prevails in all these solids. Seebeck coefficients are small as expected. Recent studies¹⁷ on La_2NiO_4 and Nd_2NiO_4 (of K_2NiF_4 structure) show that they are metallic above 500 K; La_2CuO_4 is also metallic and Pauli paramagnetic.

Rare Earth Cobaltites : Magnetic susceptibility data¹⁸⁻²⁰ on LaCoO_3 , PrCoO_3 , NdCoO_3 , and

HoCoO_3 distinctly show three regions (Fig. 4) in the $1/\chi_g - T$ curves : (i) a low temperature region where

Fig. 3. Resistivity data of metallic LaTiO_3 and LaNiO_3 . $1/\chi_g$ is essentially linear with temperature giving a lower effective magnetic moment; (ii) an intermediate temperature region where $1/\chi_g$ is independent of temperature, and (iii) a high temperature region where $1/\chi_g$ is again linear with temperature, but gives a higher effective magnetic moment. It appears that the cobalt ions exist predominantly in the low-spin ($t_{2g}^6 e_g^0$) Co^{III} state (${}^1A_{1g}$) at lower temperatures. As the temperature is increased, the diamagnetic Co^{III} ions are transformed progressively into

paramagnetic Co^{3+} ions ($t^4_{2g}e^2_g$). The energy of Co^{III} state is lower than that of the Co^{3+} state ($^5T_{2g}$); the energy difference between the two states is around 0.05 eV. The plateau in the susceptibility curve in LaCoO_3 has been identified with a variation of the population of the low *versus* high spin ions and establishment of short range order⁸. Evidence for such ordering is found by the observation of phase transitions in DTA curves as well as in other measurements. After the establishment of short range order, LaCoO_3 undergoes a symmetry change from $R\bar{3}c$ to $R\bar{3}$. A similar situation is likely to exist in the other cobaltites as well;¹⁸⁻²⁰ if so, we would expect to find ordering transitions in the corresponding temperature ranges. GdCoO_3 does not show the plateau region; however, there is a change in the slope of the susceptibility curve around 550 K where there could be an ordering transition (Fig. 4).

DTA curves^{18, 19} of LaCoO_3 , NdCoO_3 and GdCoO_3 show the presence of small endothermic transitions in the region 500-700 K, possibly due to the ordering transitions referred to earlier. In addition, the DTA curves show endothermic transitions in the 1000-1200 K range due to localized-itinerant electron transitions similar to that described in the case of LaCoO_3 .^{8, 18}

The spin-state equilibria in cobaltites can be understood by an examination of the variation of the magnetic susceptibility with temperature. Ordinarily, $\chi_g T$ of substances does not vary with temperature. However, when the proportion of the

paramagnetic species varies with temperature, $\chi_g T$, would not remain constant, but would obey the relation (1) where *n* and *m* represent the proportions of the paramagnetic (high-spin) and the diamagnetic (low-spin) ions respectively :

$$\chi_g T = \frac{N^2 \mu^2}{3R} \cdot \frac{n}{n+m} \quad (1)$$

Thus, the ratio $\text{Co}^{3+}/\text{Co}^{\text{III}}$ should keep increasing with temperature. Plots of $\chi_g T$ against temperature for LaCoO_3 , NdCoO_3 and GdCoO_3 show that $\chi_g T$ increases with temperature as expected, although not in a uniform manner (Fig. 5).

Fig. 5. $\chi_g T$ versus temperature curves of rare earth cobaltites.

Fig. 4. Inverse magnetic susceptibility-temperature curves of rare earth cobaltites.

Mossbauer spectra obtained by using the cobaltites as sources show two resonances, one centered close to 0.0 mm/sec and another around 0.5 mm/sec. (Fig. 6). Based on isomer shift systematics, we can safely assign the high energy resonance to Fe^{3+} and the low energy resonance to Fe^{II} arising out of electron-capture decay of Co^{3+} and Co^{III} respectively.¹⁸ If the assignment of the two resonance is correct, the relative intensities of the two states should comply with equation 1. However, a plot of the relative proportion of Fe^{3+} (as measured by the intensity of the high energy resonance) shows that the Fe^{3+} increases up to a temperature and then decreases, eventually becoming zero at a high temperature (Fig. 7). The temperatures at which Fe^{3+}

reaches zero concentration correspond to the localized-itinerant electron transitions.

We see that the $\chi_g T$ data and Mossbauer data show similar behaviour only in the low-temperature region. This apparent discrepancy between the susceptibility and the Mossbauer data can be understood if we propose that at high temperatures, there is electron-transfer from Co^{3+} to Co^{III} giving rise to divalent $Co^{II}(t^6_{2g}e'_g)$ and tetravalent $Co^{4+}(t^4_{2g}e^2_g)$ or $Co^{IV}(t^4_{2g}e_g^1)$ which are paramagnetic. The corresponding states of iron, Fe^{II} and Fe^{4+} (or Fe^{IV}), would, however, have isomer shifts near the zero velocity position just as Fe^{III} . Such electron-transfer *via* orbitals of e_g symmetry is compatible with $\bar{\Delta}_{cac} > \Delta_{cac}$. We, therefore, conclude that at low temperatures, the cobaltites contain mainly diamagnetic Co^{III} ions which are partly transformed to paramagnetic Co^{3+} ions up to a particular temperature. Above this temperature, an e_g electron is transferred from Co^{3+} to Co^{III} to form Co^{4+} (or Co^{IV}) and Co^{II} ion pairs. At very high temperatures, the concentration of Co^{3+} decreases below the limit of detection. Our explanation for the difference between Mossbauer and susceptibility data finds support from our studies on $HoCoO_3$. In this heavy rare earth cobaltite, the proportions of low and high spin states obtained by the two methods are identical (Fig. 8).²⁰ This shows that where there is no such correspondence, electron-transfer between Co^{3+} and Co^{III} may occur. Accordingly, the resistivity of $HoCoO_3$ is much higher than that of other cobaltites. In $HoCoO_3$, the relative proportions of Fe^{3+} and Fe^{II} remain 1 : 1 over a wide temperature range and this can be explained in terms of the small size of Ho^{3+} and consequent differences in the interaction with ligand orbitals.²⁰

Fig. 6. Mossbauer spectra of $NdCoO_3 : Co^{57}$ matched against $K_4Fe(CN)_6 \cdot 3H_2O$ single crystal absorber.

Fig. 7. Temperature variation of the relative population of high spin Fe^{3+} (with respect to other states of Fe) as seen in Mossbauer spectra.

Fig. 8. Plot of $\chi_g T$ against temperature for $HoCoO_3$. Also shown is the variation of Fe^{3+}/Fe^{II} from Mossbauer spectra.

The temperature at which Co^{3+} (or Fe^{3+}) reaches a maximum (200 K in LaCoO_3 and NdCoO_3 and 400 K in GdCoO_3) is lower than the ordering temperatures evidenced in magnetic susceptibility and Debye-Waller factor measurements or in DTA curves. Apparently, the ordering of the different spin-states of cobalt takes place after the electron-transfer from Co^{3+} to Co^{III} . However, there seems to be some relation between the ordering temperatures seen in the various measurements and the temperatures at which the relative proportion of Fe^{3+} becomes unity. In HoCoO_3 , where there is an exact correspondence between magnetic susceptibility and Mossbauer data with respect to the proportions of Co^{3+} and Co^{III} , a transition is seen when the two spin states get equally occupied (1 : 1).

As mentioned earlier, Fe^{3+} eventually becomes zero at 1210 K in LaCoO_3 corresponding to the localized \rightleftharpoons collective electron transition. At this temperature, LaCoO_3 shows a significant thermal anomaly ($\Delta H \approx 1 \text{ kcal mol}^{-1}$) and the material becomes metallic beyond this transition. NdCoO_3 and GdCoO_3 show thermal anomalies around 1000 K at which temperature Fe^{3+} becomes zero ; the ΔH of these transitions is however, considerably smaller than in LaCoO_3 . Debye-Waller factor data also clearly indicate these transitions. It appears that the high temperature transitions in these cobaltites also correspond to the localized-collective electron transition although the nature of the transitions may be different. It is relevant to note at this point that after the high-temperature transition, the cobaltites exhibit only a single resonance (corresponding to the lower energy resonance assigned to Co^{III} , Co^{4+} or Co^{II}). Under these conditions, there would be no localized e_g electrons, but σ^* bands characteristic

itinerant systems. Above this transition, the cobaltites exhibit very low resistivity and activation energy and the Seebeck coefficient is essentially constant typical of itinerant behaviour (fig. 9) ; in a

Fig. 9. Resistivity and Seebeck coefficient data on LaCoO_3 . In a few instances, the resistivity shows positive temperature coefficients as in metals. A schematic energy band diagram for LaCoO_3 and other cobaltites is shown in Fig. 10.

In the case of LaCoO_3 , NdCoO_3 and GdCoO_3 , the Debye-Waller factor increases with temperature significantly before the ordering transition peak in the DTA curves, indicating either short range ordering or a temperature region of larger atomic vibrations. In view of the susceptibility data, this transition indicated by Debye-Waller factor may be taken to indicate establishment of short range order. These phase transitions are also conveniently studied by an examination of the temperature variation of the Lamb-Mossbauer factor (area under resonance). It is significant that high-temperature transitions

Fig. 10. Band scheme for LaCoO_3 and other cobaltites at 0 K and above the localized-itinerant electron ($e_g \rightarrow \sigma^*$) transition.

(1000-1200 K) are preceded by a decrease in the Lamb-Mossbauer factor probably due to the occurrence of the large ionic vibrations similar to those discussed by Raccach and Goodenough⁸ in the case of LaCoO_3 . Above the transition temperature, the Lamb-Mossbauer factor increases indicating the establishment of long-range order. There appears to be no doubt that these transitions are electronic in origin particularly because of the absence of any structural or volume changes in the transition region. The observation of these transitions in several of these cobaltites support the hypothesis of Goodenough that the crystal field (localized) and band limits of d -electrons are distinct thermodynamic states. Accordingly, the transitions between the two states can be first or second order in rare earth cobaltites.

$\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$

$\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ compounds possess a rhombohedral structure with the rhombohedral distortion decreasing with increase in x ; when $x=0.5$, the oxide is cubic. These oxides show discontinuities in their lattice parameters around $x=0.125$. In the DTA curves, $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ compounds do not show the ordering transition seen in LaCoO_3 around 680 K beyond $x=0.05$; beyond this composition neither do they show the plateau in the $1/\chi$ - T curve as in LaCoO_3 . The endothermic transition in LaCoO_3 corresponding to the localized-itinerant electron transition around 1200 K is not seen in $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ for compositions with $x > 0.2$. In fact, beyond $x=0.3$, these oxides become metallic as indicated by resistivity and Seebeck coefficient data.

Mossbauer spectra^{21,22} of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ ($x \leq 0.125$) at room temperature show two resonances similar to LaCoO_3 , the lower velocity resonance being slightly broader due to the superposition of resonances due to tetravalent cobalt and Co^{III} (Fig. 11). For $0.125 < x < 0.50$, only a single peak located around 0.25 mm/sec is noticed; this location being close to that in $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{FeO}_3$ ($x > 0.4$) reported by Shimony and Knudsen.²³ This observation implies that the time-averaged electronic configuration of all the cobalt ions is the same. That is, the 3d hole (tetravalent cobalt) around the Sr^{2+} impurity is mobile providing evidence for the formation of the impurity band.

Mossbauer spectra of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ ($x \leq 0.125$) at 78 K were similar to the room temperature

spectra. However, for compounds with $0.125 < x < 0.50$, a magnetically split spectrum was observed against the background of a single line spectrum (Fig. 11). As x increases, the intensity of the magnetically split spectrum increases at the cost of the single line spectrum. Further, the magnetically split spectrum is seen for compositions with the positive paramagnetic Curie temperatures. Only those samples ($x > 0.125$) which give a single line spectrum at room temperature exhibit the magnetically split spectrum at 78 K. That is, the formation of the impurity band (itinerant electron behaviour) is connected with magnetic ordering.

Fig. 11. Mossbauer spectra of $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$ at 298 and 78 K. At $x=0.5$, $T_c=230 \pm 2$ K.

It is most interesting that for samples with $x > 0.125$ showing magnetic ordering, the hyperfine field (320 ± 20 kOe) and the isomer shift (0.25 ± 0.04 mm/sec) are intermediate between those for high spin Fe^{3+} and tetravalent iron. Above T_c also, the isomer shift corresponds to a similar intermediate state.

Goodenough¹³ has modified Anderson's theory¹⁴ and pointed out that if octahedral-site magnetic cations are on opposite sides of a common anion, the interaction is ferromagnetic provided one cation has completely empty e_g orbitals and the other has half-filled e_g orbitals. He postulates the existence of Co^{3+} and low-spin Co^{IV} to explain ferromagnetism in $\text{La}_{1-x}\text{Sr}_x\text{CoO}_3$. According to Goodenough, Co^{3+} transforms to Co^{2+} on the transfer of a $2p$ electron

from oxygen while the Co^{IV} would transform to Co^{III}. The observed Mossbauer spectra, however, do not support this mechanism, since we would expect to see more than one six-finger pattern below T_c whatever be the relative values of the relaxation time and Larmor precession time. According to Zener's double exchange mechanism,²⁴ there would be simultaneous transfer of an electron from the oxygen 2*p* orbital to Co⁴⁺ and from the Co³⁺ to the 2*p* orbital of oxygen, the resonance energy between the configurations, Co³⁺ - O²⁻ - Co⁴⁺ ↔ Co⁴⁺ - O²⁻ - Co³⁺ being large if spins are parallel. The observation of one six-finger pattern below T_c may be taken to indicate that the above transformation is very rapid. The resonance energy would be maximum if the tetravalent cobalt had the intermediate spin configuration, Co^{IV} (t⁴_{2g}e¹_g) and this configuration would permit ferromagnetism by Anderson-Goodenough as well as by Zener's mechanism. However, since we do not see any break in the resistivity curve at T_c, this seems to be against Zener's mechanism. A model based on itinerant electron ferromagnetism would explain all the observed features of La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO₃. The real difference between fast double exchange and the itinerant models is, however, not too clear.

The ferromagnetic component in La_{1-x}Sr_xCoO₃ (0.125 < x < 0.50) increases with x. This is because, the Sr²⁺-rich regions are associated with ferromagnetic clusters while the La³⁺-rich regions are associated with paramagnetism. Apparently, the ferromagnetic particle size distribution curve shifts towards lower particle size as Sr²⁺ content decreases. Variation of the paramagnetic-ferromagnetic ratio with temperature also supports this conclusion. We also find that ferromagnetism cannot be observed below x=0.125. It is at this composition that the paramagnetic Curie temperature changes sign. Around this composition, we also see the structural discontinuities and changes in electron transport properties. The La³⁺-rich and Sr²⁺-rich regions would be associated with localized and itinerant electrons respectively, making the material 'electronically inhomogeneous' by virtue of coexistence of the localized and itinerant electrons.

Catalytic Properties of Rare Earth Cobaltites :

We have examined the catalytic activity of various rare earth cobaltites²⁶ and their solid solutions for the oxidation of CO. We find that NdCoO₃ and

HoCoO₃ are much better catalysts than LaCoO₃. The catalytic activity seems to be related to the spin state populations in the cobaltites²⁶. In HoCoO₃ and NdCoO₃, the relative proportion of high spin Co³⁺ reaches unity at fairly low temperatures.

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